

PSYCHOLOGICAL ADVICE ON PREVENTING CONFLICTS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. This article looks at how to prevent teenage parent-child conflict. The origin of conflicts between father and daughter, mother and son. The hobbies and interests of teenage children, and a new emotion emerging in adolescent psychology, is self-awareness. Studying the attitude of father to mother from conflict situations in the family using an asychological approach. Information is provided on V. Sukhomlinsky's identification of the basic personality traits.

Keywords. adolescence , parents, emancipation, personality traits, physiological, physical.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ КОНСУЛЬТАЦИИ ПО ПРЕДОТВРАЩЕНИЮ КОНФЛИКТОВ МЕЖДУ ПОДРОСТКАМИ И МОЛОДЫМИ ЛЮДЬМИ В СЕМЬЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются способы предотвращения подросткового детско-родительского конфликта. Происхождение конфликтов между отцом и дочерью, матерью и сыном. Хобби и интересы детей-подростков, а также новая эмоция, возникающая в подростковой психологии, — это самосознание. Изучение отношения отца к матери из конфликтных ситуаций в семье с использованием асихологического подхода. Представлена информация по выявлению В. Сухомлинским основных качеств личности.

Ключевые слова. подростковый возраст, родители, эмансипация, особенности личности, физиологический, физический.

Disagreements with parents arise because the teenager feels big and wants to take the place of his parents. Of course, parents don't like this. Disagreements arise between parents and children . sometimes it can be conflicts between father and daughter, mother and son. They say that a girl is closer to her father, and a boy is closer to his mother. But over time, that is, in adulthood, the child begins to forget about it.

Because he directed his feelings towards other people outside the family. He begins to try to lose his relationship with his parents. If at home a teenager treats the child kindly and tenderly, taking into account the child's age, if the child's wishes are taken into account depending on the circumstances, if the child is treated as an individual, he will notice this and try to follow a good

path. Otherwise, the teenager will find something else to do on the street and there is a high probability of going down the wrong path.

Undoubtedly, the role and influence of the family in the formation and development of the unique spirituality of any people is immeasurable. Because the purest and purest feelings of a person, the first life concepts and ideas are first formed in the bosom of the family. [] .

In our mentality, especially girls are prepared only for marriage. As a result, our girls also start thinking about getting married and starting a family when they start a family. It is no secret that our ancestors raised their children based on our national values, and as a result, many great people grew up among them. As an example, unfortunately, today's superficial, indifferent attitude towards family formation, treating it as just a biological phenomenon is the reason for the increase in the number of divorces. To prevent this, it is necessary to create "Family Training Centers" in microdistricts, settlements and higher educational institutions.

We call the period of adolescence a difficult period, but we do not realize that we are the cause of the emergence and slow passage of this interval. If we devote a little time to our children and find a way to please them, we will raise and mature people who will benefit our society tomorrow.

Adolescence is the period from 10-11 to 14-15 years. For most students, the transition to adolescence usually begins in 5th grade. "Now he is not a child - he is not yet an adult" - this formula indicates the nature of adolescence. At this age, dramatic changes in the development of a teenager begin to occur. These changes are physiological and psychological changes. **Modern medicine studies the onset of anatomical and physiological changes in the body from the age of 7. Accordingly, they believe that it is necessary to determine adolescence not by the calendar, but by sexual changes in the body.**

As a result of the acceleration of physiological changes in the body at this age, the child feels excited, wakes up in high spirits, and sometimes feels the urge to fall to the ground.

During this period, the child requires more attention. He considers himself an adult and demands an adult attitude towards his personality. But in school, college or high school, and even at home, his position remains the same. As a result, the child will begin adolescence . The teenage crisis gives rise to emancipation, grouping with peers and a reaction to hobbies. In the case of an emancipation reaction, the child wants to get out of the control of adults and gain independence, in which his "I" manifests itself. Even slight harassment from an adult can cause a child's behavior disorder.

Grouping with peers develops in the child the skills of mutual movement, subordination to group order, gaining respect and taking a position of his own free will. The child develops self-

esteem. He values the opinions of his peers more than the criticism of adults.

Hobbies - doing something is very important. Thanks to him, the child develops interests and individual abilities.

Types of hobbies: intellectual and aesthetic, i.e. music, painting, history, technology; collect something; eccentric, that is, he can be the center of attention in the form of interest in extravagant clothing.

Knowing the interests of teenagers improves mutual understanding between them and adults.

A new feeling emerging in adolescent psychology is self-awareness. Self-awareness is the main goal of adolescence. At this time, a person discovers a new self, tries to find out his strengths and weaknesses. He begins to compare himself with other people, becomes interested in himself, and looks for a suitable friend.

As a rule, society's assessment of a child is more important than the assessment of a teacher or parent. At this age, good conditions are created for the child to develop organizational, business and other personal qualities.

V. Sukhomlinsky describes the main personality traits this way.

1. Disobedience to ignorance, on the one hand, is combined with the ability not to accept it emotionally, and on the other hand, with the inability to solve difficult life situations.

2. The teenager wants to be good, strives for the ideal, but does not like to receive a proper education.

3. A teenager wants to be an individual. He wants to do something heroic, romantic, unusual. Despite the fact that there is a demand for the process and a desire to be self-confident, the teenager does not yet know how to achieve this.

4. A teenager has a contrast between richness of desires and limited strength. This is the reason for the diversity and inconstancy of interests. The teenager is afraid of discovering that he is incapable. He loves himself very much, and behind this lies the need for help. This may be hidden behind a display of reliability and determination.

5. The teenager has a combination of romantic feelings and rude actions. Enjoys beauty and constantly relates to it. But he is ashamed of his feelings. He believes that these feelings are characteristic of young children. He is afraid that he will be considered too emotional and hides behind rudeness.

The influx of physical energy makes it work.

When working with teenagers, it is necessary to take into account their age and personality characteristics, the main thing is the psychological renewal of this age.

By this time, the teenager's body also undergoes many changes: acne appears, various unpleasant odors begin to emanate from the body. That is why, when school hours are over, the teacher should also talk about personal hygiene.

At this age, a child undergoes a lot of psychological changes, and we will look at this.

First of all, children of this age are shy and easily upset. He gets offended even by trifles and attaches great importance to it. He is ashamed of his appearance, his movements are constrained. Because he still can't control his body like he used to. Likewise, a teenager cannot control his emotions. He considers himself a great person and demands the same attitude from others.

Physiological changes are the beginning of puberty and, in connection with this, the perfect development and growth of all organs of the body, reshaping of cells and structures of the body. Changes in the body are directly related to changes in the teenage endocrine system. During this period, the function of one of the 10 endocrine glands, the pituitary gland, is activated. Its activity enhances the growth of body tissues and the functioning of important endocrine glands (thyroid gland, kidney growth and gonads). As a result, height growth accelerates and puberty occurs (development of the genital organs, appearance of secondary sex glands). Teenagers try to behave like adults. They tend to demonstrate their abilities, skills and capabilities to a certain extent to their peers and teachers. This situation is easy to see by simple observation. By studying the psychological characteristics characteristic of adolescence, one can understand the ways of formation, development and maturation of a teenager's personality and the direct influence of the biological and social factors influencing it. During this period, the teenager is in a situation where he has said goodbye to a happy childhood, but has not yet found his place in adulthood. Adolescence is characterized by its psychological manifestations, which are called "Transition period", "Crisis period", "Difficult period". Because there are also inappropriate behavior in adolescents of this age, cases of mental explosion due to the inability to find their place in new conditions. At one time, L. S. Vygotsky called this situation a crisis of mental development. The peculiarities of their behavior in adolescence cannot be explained mainly by the onset of sexualization. Puberty influences adolescent behavior as a major biological factor, and this effect is indirect rather than direct. Adolescence is often characterized by stubbornness, obstinacy, denial of one's own shortcomings, and belligerence. The appearance of an aggressive attitude towards adults, unconscious behavioral symptoms such as negativism are not signs that arise directly as a result of puberty, but indirectly under the influence of the social conditions in which a teenager lives: at the expense of his peers, his position in various communities, 11 - these are character traits that arise due to relationships with adults, school and family relationships. By changing these

social conditions, it is possible to directly influence the behavior of adolescents.

The leading activities in adolescence are study, communication and work. The main task of teenagers' communication is to define and assimilate the basic norms of friendship and camaraderie. The main feature of Teen 12 communication is that it follows a complete friendship code. Teenagers' communication with parents and adults is mainly based on their sense of adulthood. They are very concerned about restrictions on their rights, opposition and opposition from adults. But despite this, they feel the need for adult support in communication. Joint activities help teenagers understand adults better. The teenager feels a great need to share with adults about the changes taking place in him, about the problems that concern him, but he will never be the first to do this. The teenager complains strongly about being treated like a small child. Teenage communication is ultimately characterized by variability. Imitating someone else's behavior is typical of adolescence. They often imitate the behavior of adults they know and love. This orientation is certainly present in the communication and attitude of adults, but they differ from adults in their emotionality. In a group of peers and classmates, the teenager shows complaisance. Being dependent and dependent on his group, the teenager is ready to agree with the general opinion of this group and always follow its decision. The group often helps to form a sense of "We" in a teenager and strengthens his inner state. The choice of friends for a teenager is very important. A friend is very valuable during adolescence. Friends constantly feel the need to be close in spirit and heart. This desire can be seen in the way teenage friends ask and see each other (handshakes and hugs), try to sit together and take walks together. Many of these very close relationships, traces of joint actions of adolescents in the formation of personality, remain in the heart and memory of a person for life. Teenagers have a great need for the trust of adults. The most favorable conditions for the influence of adults on adolescents and their upbringing are shared labor. If younger children are satisfied with their role as helpers, adolescents, especially older ones, will be satisfied with the fact that they act as equals to adults and can act as a substitute when needed. If adults lead teenagers in an equal, friendly, understanding and reasonable way, teenagers will look at it positively, but if this leadership is based on the superiority of the adult's desires, then they will completely resist. This resistance can often lead to negative consequences and sometimes even depression. This situation often arises in families where parents have an authoritarian position. Teenagers who grew up in many such families find it somewhat more difficult to move through life independently, realize their plans, and take on complex responsibilities. They often have difficulty overcoming intellectual problems. During adolescence, children's position in personal and work relationships with people around them changes. Now teenagers begin to engage in more serious work, devoting less time to games and leisure, and their cognitive processes begin

to develop rapidly. Reading occupies a large place in the lives of teenagers. The main motive for reading to teenagers is to prepare them for the types of reading that make them feel and express their greatness. They like forms of learning that primarily involve independence. Compared to children of other ages, the successful learning of subjects by adolescents depends on the teacher's ability to explain educational material.

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